

Innovativeness and Survival of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Nigeria

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Abstract:

The study investigated the relationship between innovativeness and the survival of small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Port Harcourt. The cross-sectional survey method was adopted. A sample size of eighty was drawn from a population of one hundred employees using the Taro Yamane formula. The questionnaire was the main instrument for data collection and data obtained were analyzed using the SPSS. Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was used to test the hypotheses. Our findings revealed a strong and positive relationship between innovativeness and the measures of survival of small and medium scale enterprises. We concluded that innovativeness significantly and proportionately predicts the organizational performance and success level of SMEs. We recommended that firms should undertake more innovative and enterprising activities. Managers should encourage employees to think beyond the present situation. They should be willing to tolerate mistakes and reward new ideas contributed towards innovation and organizational survival. The government ought to as a matter of criticality help planned business visionaries to have admittance to the public purse to back them up. This could enable them to implement their innovative ideas.

Keywords: innovativeness, survival, enterprises, success.

1. INTRODUCTION

At the centre of every economy, a subtle concept that attracts the attention of all tiers of government, desire of citizens and attention of scholars is Entrepreneurship, this is borne out of the fact that evidence point to the positive influx of entrepreneurship in an economy which manifest through reduction of unemployment via job creation and promotes output level across sectors in an economy thus stimulating Growth and fostering national Development as asserted by Zubair (2014) and Baig, (2007), Entrepreneurial endeavours are largely dominated by the private sector and usually mushrooms on the Small Scale Enterprises and other sectorial activities like the agricultural sector that host few employees and are characterized by small capital base.

In the perspective of Ayyagari, Beck, and Demircic. (2003), Small and Medium Enterprise (SMEs) make-up the vast majority of firms that operates in Nigeria, they represent about 90 percent of the industrial sector as regards a number of enterprises. They, however, contribute only 1% (percent) of the Gross Domestic Products (GDP). This is a far cry from other nations such as Indonesia, Thailand, and India where their SMEs are vibrant and has contributed about 40% (percent). Besides the poor performance of the SMEs, they are increasingly experiencing high birth rate and mortality rate among the different type of firms operating in Nigeria. Most SMEs in Nigeria die within the duration of their first and fifth year of existence, representing ninety-five percent (95%); while only about five to ten percent (5-10%) is quoted to have succeeded (NBS,2013).

Nowduri et al., (2012) assert that SMEs facilitate easy distribution of economic wealth and the decentralization of economic growth. They are responsible for most of the breakthroughs and advances in new products and process. SMEs contribute to the alleviation of poverty through employment creation, provision of flexible and specialized service to large-scale industries. By participating mostly in the untapped markets, SMEs have stimulated economic development and national growth. Their impacts have been less satisfactory, and their performances have fallen short of expectation particularly in the developing economies of the world (Manbula, 2002).

Fatoki and Odeyemi (2010) are of the view that SMEs in the developing countries face two major challenges: Internal factors such as lack of entrepreneurial competencies, management skill, commitment, resources, strategies choice and External factors including competitors, culture, technology, infrastructure, policies inconsistencies in Government and official bureaucracy.

To provide answers to these challenges Hornsby *et al.*, (2009) assert that entrepreneurial organization should be risk-tolerant and innovative oriented, such attitudes instill flexibility and grant individuals and team the freedom to exercise their creativity thereby championing promising ideas that result into profitable ventures. Man, Lau & Chan (2002) identified innovativeness as one of the important factors that could account for organizational survival. Several types of research on organizational survival have taken place in the recent past (Damanpour, 1991; Zahra and Covin, 1995; Man, Lau & Chan, 2002). Many of these studies revealed that innovativeness has a positive and significant impact on organizational survival.

Much has been written about innovativeness and organizational survival. Despite the increase in prior publications and studies, the extent to which innovativeness influence organizational survival has not been sufficiently clarified (Zahra and Covin, 1995). Most of the studies in the entrepreneurship literature tend to focus on SMEs in America and other developed countries with very little studies with respect to developing countries such as Nigeria. Furthermore, previous studies focused on established corporate organizations and medium-large organizations, leaving out SMEs which is considered to be a very powerful means of national development. This study, therefore, examines the relationship between innovativeness and survival of small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria to bridge the existing knowledge gap in the literature.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Innovativeness refers to the willingness and readiness of an individual or organization to support new creative ideas, novelty that result to the development of new products and services, new production methods and new procedure by using new technology or break away from prior technologies that most likely result into new products, services and new market by investing in experimentation, research and training (Lumpkin and Dess, 2001). Schumpeter (1934) was the first to articulate the roles of the innovative entrepreneurs in the market process and coined the definition of innovation. He argued against the neoclassical theory and proposed an economic process he called “creative destruction” or “creative innovation” which he described as the propensity by which entrepreneur innovate their business and the new entry of goods and services, new source of supply and new methods of production that discard the old products and services. Rauch *et al.* (2009) maintained that innovativeness involves the pursuit of novelties or a creative behavior that seeks to find new solutions to challenges confronting organization and an attempt to change the existing status quo of a given area of an organization. He further affirms that creativity is the starting point of innovation and a means to unlock the entrepreneurial potential of the individuals in the organizations. Innovativeness reflects sets of actions created through which organization seeks to exploit entrepreneurial opportunities that rival competitors have not spotted or identified (Covin and Slevin, 1984). Innovativeness creates new ventures and organizational renewal which is considered as strategic policies that facilitate competitive advantages for the organization by giving firms the first mover advantages and growth (Lumpkin and Dess, 2001). They further argued that innovation is the implementation of creative inspiration, for without innovation an enterprise and its products quickly become obsolete in the long term. Amabili *et al.* (2005), supporting this view, assert that organizational innovativeness is a key factor in gaining and sustaining competitive advantage in the marketplace. Innovation enables firms to renew their operations in the marketplace, thereby improving their profitability and growth. Hult, Harley, and Knight (2004) identified innovativeness as the development of new competitive strategies that creates value for the firm. **From the foregoing, the working definition of innovativeness in this paper refers to the extent to which an organization creates new ventures and renews existing products and processes to remain competitive in the market.**

Maheshwari (1980) argued that the concept of Organizational survival is a multiple dimensional concept with no common definition, making it elusive that there is no one single way of defining organizational survival. This fact may be due to the many criteria used to measure organizational survival and the many definitions available for the concept. A firm is successful if it is able to attain its goals (Amah, 2014). Evidence found in the entrepreneurial, management and business literature confirmed that organizational survival and organizational performance are very narrowly connected (Perren, 2000; Jennings and Beaver, 1993). The concepts of success and performance are usually used as synonyms for each other or interchangeably. Previous analyses in the entrepreneurial literature used various terms to describe organizational survival such as

entrepreneurial success and the achievement of owner's success goal etc. Man et al., (2002) therefore argued that an organization is considered successful when it realizes an optimal level of performance in respect of profitability, growth, and development to the satisfaction of the owner. Also, according to De-smet et al., (2006), revealed that success could be defined as an organizational ability to operate effectively and efficiently, coping adequately and being able to withstand the environmental turbulences by being flexible and adapting to change which may result to growth. Imoisili (1978) defined Organizational survival as organization's ability to achieve sustainable growth and realization of its goals which leads to eventual superior performance. Similarly, Beaver and Jennings (1995) are of the view that the most commonly adopted description of organizational survival has much to do with financial viability and growth with sufficient profits than other factors such as owner's satisfaction, employee satisfaction, etc. Simpson *et al.*, (2004) maintained that organizational survival is a multi-dimensional concept which has no single significant element as its measures of analysis. He further stated that most managers and entrepreneurial literature wrongly measure the success of small businesses based on the methods and procedures developed for large companies that have clear, precise, financial goals and objectives. Simpson et al., (2004) noted that there are two major indicators of success: the financial and non-financial measures. The financial performance measures of organizational survival include: profitability, returns on capital, the productivity of assets, sales margins, net operating margin, etc. while the non-financial indicators are the degree of employee satisfaction, ability to retain management talent, the degree of customer satisfaction, owners' satisfaction, superior products, and services, etc. On the other hand, determination of the right criteria is paramount in getting the accurate result. According to Masuo, *et al.* (2001) to avoid errors in determining the measures, the selections of appropriate measure should depend on the type or nature of the organization under review, the various environmental factors, cultures, management styles, capital availability, technology and goal of the organization should be considered. This argument is based on the fact that every organization has its different characteristics, goals, and constituencies. Paige and Littrell (2002) assert that some scholars include subjective (intrinsic) criteria such as freedom and independence, being one's own boss, controlling one's own future; while the objective (extrinsic) factors such as increase profitability and wealth as the criteria for organizational survival. Cameron (1978) suggested that there are other criteria that could be used in the measurement of organizational survival such as effectiveness and efficiency. An organization can only survive when it is able to adapt to the environment and satisfy its customers. For the purpose of this study, Organizational survival will be defined as the ability of a firm to realize and actualize its outcome and expectations in line with its mission, goals, and objectives despite the prevailing environmental conditions. The following hypotheses were derived.

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between innovativeness and customer satisfaction of SMEs in Port Harcourt.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between innovativeness and Adaptability of SMEs in Port Harcourt.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a cross-sectional survey of the quasi-experimental design. This method is adopted because the respondents who are in their private business are exposed to complex relationships which are not subject to manipulation (Baridam, 2001). This study aimed at examining the relationship between of innovation on organizational survival in SMEs in Rivers State. The population for this study comprises of all the Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Rivers State, registered with the Rivers State Ministry of Trade and Commerce. However, for easy accessibility, the accessible population consists of 120 respondents, (owners-partners, managers, and key officers) from the 20 selected SMEs within Rivers State, using purposive sampling technique. It is assumed that responses obtained from the sample respondent would be representative of the opinions of all SMEs operating in Rivers State. The respondents are in a position to express their opinion about the questions relating to the research instrument. The sampling procedure adopted in this study is the Simple random sampling techniques. This approach is to enable each member of the population to have an equal chance of being selected. Our accessible population for this study consists of 102 owners-partners, managers and key

officers in twenty (20) selected SMEs firm in Rivers State, adopting a purposive sampling technique. It was from the accessible population that the sample size for the study is drawn. The sampling procedure adopted was the simple random sampling method. A sample size of eighty (80) owners-partners, managers, and key officers was drawn from the twenty (20) selected SMEs under review. The sample size was determined using the sample size determination formula of Taro Yamens formula at 0.05 level of significance (Baridam, 2001)

RESEARCH RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between innovativeness and customer satisfaction of SMEs in Port Harcourt.

Table 4.1 Correlation Output of innovativeness and customer satisfaction of SMEs in Rivers State.

			INNOVATI VENESS	CUSTOMER SATISFACT ION
Spearman's rho	INNOVATIVENESS	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.983**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	80	80
	CUSTOMER SATISFACTION	Correlation Coefficient	.983**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	80	80

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Statistical Package for Social Sciences (version 22) Extract.

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between innovativeness and Adaptability of SMEs in Port Harcourt.

Table 4.2 Correlation Output of innovativeness and Adaptability of SMEs in Rivers State.

			INNOVATIVE NESS	ADAPTABILITY
Spearman's rho	INNOVATIVENES S	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.975**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	80	80
	ADAPTABILITY	Correlation Coefficient	.975**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	80	80

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Statistical Package for Social Sciences (version 22) Extract.

Hypothesis One: Relationship between Innovation and Customer Satisfaction- The Table 4.1 above illustrates the analysis for the association between innovativeness and customer satisfaction of SMEs in Rivers State where Rho = .983 and p = 0.000. The findings show a very positive and significant association between both variables. This means that increase in Innovation is associated with an increase in Customer Satisfaction.

Hypothesis Two: Relationship between Innovation and Adaptability- Table 4.2 above illustrates the analysis

for the association between innovativeness and Adaptability of SMEs in Rivers State where $Rho = .975$ and $p = 0.000$. The findings show a very positive and significant association between both variables. There is a significant relationship between innovativeness and Adaptability of SMEs in Port Harcourt. This implies that increase in Innovation is associated with an increase in Adaptability.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Innovativeness: Customer Service and Adaptability

In hypotheses one, our findings revealed a strong and significant relationship between innovativeness and customer satisfaction. This is in agreement with the works of (Muhammed et al. 2015) who argued that those entrepreneurs who are more innovative will have a better chance of offering their customers satisfaction. Dhliwayo and Vuuren (2007) went further to say that firms that encourage innovativeness and builds it into their culture will have a more satisfied customer base than firms that are not innovative.

In reference to hypotheses two, our findings here revealed a significant relationship between innovativeness and adaptability. This finding agrees with the work of (Chononye et al., 2016) who argued that innovative firms will have the ability to adapt to changing environment more than firms that are less innovative. Considering how the business environment has continued to change and remain highly dynamic, (Schwarz et al., 2009) believes that firms with high level of innovation will easily manage and adapt to changes in the business environment. Innovativeness helps firms to adjust to changes in customer taste and desire and also adapt to organizational changes.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study evaluated the interrelationship between innovativeness and organizational survival by taking a cross-sectional analysis at the interplay between innovativeness, and measures of Organizational survival which includes adaptability, and customer satisfaction using a sample of twenty firms and primary data sourced variables.

Based on the findings, this paper concludes that innovativeness significantly influences a firm's success and proportionately predicts the organizational performance and success level of a firm. Innovation by Nigerian entrepreneurs ensures organizational survival and success.

In light of the above, the study recommends that

- Firms are given enabling the environment to encourage innovativeness.
- Those with innovative ideas be given access to finance to enable them to implement their innovative ideas.
- The government should make available necessary current data to enable firms to have adequate information to plan with.

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